

Studies on method development for determination of tellurium by differential pulse polarography in waste samples

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Abstract : A study of electroreduction behaviour of tellurium(IV) in presence of dimethylformamide at a dropping mercury electrode shows the possibility of developing a voltammetric method for the determination of tellurium at very low concentrations. A limit of quantification of 4 µg/L was achieved using differential pulse polarography.

Keywords : Tellurium, dimethylformamide, DPP.

Introduction

The aim of the work was to develop suitable voltammetric methods of simple approach for the determination of ultra trace metals which are usually present at very low concentration. The determination of chromium¹, arsenic², mercury³ and osmium⁴ has already been reported. In the present work attention was focussed on tellurium determination, which has a definite toxicological importance. Tellurium ions are very hazardous and ingestion of tellurium compounds can result in severe permanent damages⁵. In modification to our earlier work on voltammetric determination of tellurium⁶, herein it was observed that the limit of quantification could be lowered down from 20 µg/L to 4 µg/L in presence of selective complexing reagent by using differential pulse polarography (DPP).

The commonly employed complexing reagent for voltammetric determination of tellurium is quinolinol and its derivatives. Wang⁷ has reported cathodic stripping voltammetric determination of tellurium using selective adsorption of tellurium-8-quinolinol at a hanging mercury drop electrode. Yang⁸ has also used a tosflex/8-quinolinol mercury film electrode in determination of tellurium by cathodic stripping voltammetry. Further, Khoo and Ye⁹ have described determination of tellurium at a poly(3,3-diamino benzidine) film-modified electrode by differential pulse voltammetry. We have used the complexing ability of dimethylformamide to study the

Te^{IV}/Te⁰ system at dropping mercury electrode. It has resulted in development of a suitable DPP method for sub µg level determination of tellurium in aqueous matrices.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical characteristics and choice of medium :

The reduction of tellurium(IV) was studied in different complexing media and dimethylformamide in alkaline medium was found to be most adequate as against the other investigated media, such as thiosemicarbazide, thioacetamide and urea. These media were studied keeping in view the fact that tellurium forms sufficiently stable complexes with ligands containing nitrogen and sulfur and measurable at dropping electrode¹⁰. Polarographic characteristics of Te^{IV} in different media are given in Table 1¹¹. It concluded that electroreduction of tellurium(IV) occurred at more negative potentials i.e. > -1.7 V where reduction wave might be merged with final current rise. It was thus not convenient for voltammetric measurement of tellurium. However in the presence of dimethyl-

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics of Te^{IV}

Sl. no.	Complexing media	-E _{1/2} (V)	i _d (µA)
1.	0.06 M Dimethylformamide	1.16	1.46
2.	0.01 M Thiosemicarbazide	1.72	1.23
3.	0.01 M Thioacetamide	1.74	0.86
4.	0.01 M Urea	1.73	1.31

Te^{IV} = 1 × 10⁻⁴ M ; Medium = 0.01 M NaOH

formamide, tellurium(IV) showed a well-defined polarographic wave for its reduction to tellurium(0) at -1.16 V. The wave height increased with the concentration of dimethylformamide upto 0.06 M in 0.01 M NaOH. Higher concentration of the reagent did not change the limiting current. All the measurements were therefore made at this concentration.

The wave appeared to be diffusion controlled. The plot of E vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ is drawn in Fig. 1. It gave a straight line with a slope of 0.04 V against the ideal value of 0.015 V as the slope corresponds to $0.059/n^{1/2}$. Thus electrode reaction was not fully reversible.

Fig. 1. Log plot analysis of Te^{IV} -dimethylformamide reduction wave in 0.01 M NaOH.

Optimum DPP conditions : Method development :

DPP reduction of tellurium(IV) in presence of dimethylformamide in 0.01 M NaOH, gave a sharp DP peak at -1.16 V. Linearity of peak current versus concentration was noticed in range of 0.004 ppm to 26 ppm. The calibration curve characteristics were as follows : slope, 0.1018 ; intercept, 0.0512 ; coefficient of correlation (r), 0.9989 . It has been drawn in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Calibration curve of tellurium(IV), concentration vs peak current, in 0.06 M dimethylformamide - 0.01 M NaOH.

Interference study :

The analysis of industrial wastes by voltammetry has revealed the presence of lead, cadmium and zinc^{13,14}. Similarly, copper might be associated with tellurium as latter is obtained from anode slime of Cu refining¹⁵. Therefore it is appropriate to study interference of these metal ions during the voltammetric determination of tellurium. The DP peak of Cu^{II} in complexing medium of dimethylformamide in sodium hydroxide was noticed at more positive potential ($+0.07$ V), illustrating no interference. Peak potential of Zn^{II} was noted at -0.97 V, which is well-separated from that of Te^{IV} at -1.16 V. Lead and cadmium also gave distinguishable peaks (E_{ps} : Pb^{II} , -0.32 V; Cd^{II} , -0.53 V). It has been clarified in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. DP polarogram of tellurium(IV) in presence of copper, lead, cadmium and zinc in 0.06 M dimethylformamide - 0.01 M NaOH. Cu^{II} , 7 ppm; Pb^{II} , 16 ppm; Cd^{II} , 9 ppm; Zn^{II} , 5 ppm and Te^{IV} , 15 ppm. Modulation amplitude, 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; drop time, 0.5 s and scan rate 12 mV/s.

Accuracy and precision :

The reproducibility of the method was evaluated by determining tellurium in a test solution of known concentration under the optimized experimental conditions. The obtained data were in good agreement in terms of measurements with a relative error of 2.44% , inferring that method is precise and accurate.

Limit of determination :

The limit of quantification tellurium was found to be 4 µg/L.

Analytical applications :

The devised optimum voltammetric conditions consisting of polarographic medium, calibration linearity, reproducibility and detection limit, were applied to analyse tellurium in industrial wastes.

DPP method was found more suitable to stripping voltammetry in determination of tellurium because of higher negative reduction potential of Te^{IV} at -1.16 V. Other metals present in waste samples such as copper, lead and zinc would also be thus deposited on the surfaces of electrode forming intermetallic compound and causing significant interference during the stripping process and voltammetric measurements¹⁶.

Voltammetric measurements :

The prepared samples were taken into the polarographic cell with 0.06 M dimethylformamide in 0.01 M sodium hydroxide and DP polarograms were recorded from -0.6 to -2.0 V. The peak currents were noted at -1.16 V after making blank corrections. The concentrations were determined by standard addition method¹⁷. The results of determination of tellurium are presented in Table 2. The

Table 2. DPP determination of tellurium in industrial waste samples

Sample	Te (ppm)	
	DPP ± SD	CV (%)
Bohra Industry	0.088 ± 0.006	7.13
Kaushik Industry	0.060 ± 0.005	7.89
Mahi Industry	0.108 ± 0.006	5.42

No. of determinations = 5

Cu^{II}, 0.44 ppm; Pb^{II}, 0.084 ppm; Cd^{II}, 0.002 ppm; Zn^{II}, 0.547 ppm.

results of determination of tellurium by present method are also in good agreement with other techniques including differential pulse polarography reported by Nagaosa and Ono¹⁸ in terms of detection limit (0.005 µg/mL). Further, since the method is based on the extraction of dimethylthiocarbamates of Te^{IV} into ethyl acetate medium, it might be subject to numerous interferences in the process.

Validation :

The results of DPP determination of tellurium in dif-

ferent samples of industrial waste were further verified by carrying out comparison studies with UV-Vis spectrophotometric method. The data so obtained are compared in Table 3. The suggested DPP method for determination

Table 3. Comparison of results of determination of tellurium by DPP and UV-Vis spectrophotometry

Sample	UV-Vis (ppm)			DPP (ppm)
	Min.	Max.	Ave ± SD	
1.	0.080	0.097	0.088 ± 0.007	0.088
2.	0.055	0.069	0.061 ± 0.005	0.060
3.	0.102	0.119	0.109 ± 0.006	0.108

Sample 1, 2, 3 from Bohra, Kaushik and Mahi Industry.

of tellurium is specific, rapid and convenient due to simple sample preparation, no interference from major ions and low cost of instrumentation.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

A microprocessor based pulse polarographic analyzer (Model CL-362) in combination with a drop-timer assembly, all of Elico Limited, Hyderabad, India, was used for voltammetric measurements. Voltammograms were recorded by an Epson printer (Epson-LX-300+II). The instrumental settings for DPP were as follows : a DME was used as working electrode; pulse amplitude, 50 mV; drop time, 0.5 s; scan rate, 12 mV/s, and charging current compensation, 20%. Potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode throughout.

A UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model-108) of Systronics, India, was also employed for sample analysis. It has a wavelength range from 190-900 nm. The tungsten-halogen deuterium lamp and wide range photomultiplier were used as the light source and detector, respectively. The spectral band width of resolution was 0.5 nm.

Sample collection :

Industrial waste water samples were collected in polyethylene containers from different metal industries located in Basni Industrial Area of Jodhpur. Glasswares were soaked in 2 M nitric acid for at least one week and washed several times prior to use to avoid contamination. Collected samples were filtered in order to separate any suspended particulate matter and acidified with HCl to pH ~2 for storage¹⁹.

Sample treatment :

A 50 ml aliquot of sample was treated with 1 ml of oxidizing mixture of nitric acid and sulphuric acid to destroy the biological and organic matters. The contents were heated on a hot plate until the solution fumed and then were transferred to a volumetric flask with requisite volume of distilled water²⁰.

Test solutions were deaerated for 20 min by passing nitrogen. It was purified by bubbling through a vanadous chloride scrubbing solution²¹. Chemicals used were of analytical grade. Stock solution of tellurium was prepared from tellurium dioxide of Aldrich. All experiments were carried at ± 298 K.

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References

1. P. Sharma and R. C. Kapoor, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 51.
2. P. Sharma, *Anal. Sci.*, 1995, **11**, 261.
3. P. Sharma, S. Vyas and S. Sangneria, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 1997, **68**, 391.
4. P. Sharma and A. Agarwal, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2004, **20**, 145.
5. I. I. Nazarnko and A. V. Ermakova, "Selenium and Tellurium", Wiley, New York, 1972.
6. P. Sharma and A. Agarwal, *Anal. Lett.*, 2006, **39**, 1421.
7. J. Wang, *Electroanalysis*, 1994, **6**, 405.
8. H. Y. Yang, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1998, **358**, 285.
9. S. B. Khoo and R. D. Ye, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2002, **453**, 209.
10. D. I. Ryabchikov and I. I. Nazarenko, *Russian Rev.*, 1964, **33**, 55.
11. V. Kherwa, PhD Thesis, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur, 2010.
12. R. C. Kapoor and B. S. Agarwal, "Principles of Polarography", Wiley Eastern Limited, New Delhi, 1991.
13. P. Sharma, S. Kumar and C. Rawat, *Poll. Res.*, 1990, **8**, 157.
14. P. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 707.
15. J. Emsley, "The Elements", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1988.
16. A. J. Bard and L. R. Faulkner, "Electrochemical Methods : Fundamentals and Applications", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, Singapore, 2004.
17. H. Willard, L. Merit and J. Dean, "Instrumental Methods of Analysis", 2nd ed., D. Van Nostrand, New York, 1974.
18. Y. Nagaosa and M. Ono, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1987, **36**, 735.
19. H. W. Numberg, "Approved Voltammetric Methods for the Determination of some Toxic Trace Metals", Nuclear Research Center Publication, K.F.A., Juelich, 1977.
20. A. E. Greenberg, J. J. Connors and D. Jenkins (eds.), "Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste Water", 15th ed., American Public Health Association, New York, 1981.
21. Application Notes - 156, EG & G, PARC, New Jersey, 1979.